

Identification and Intervention of Phonological Processes among Children with Spastic Cerebral Palsy

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Abstract

The current study sought to detect and intervene the phonological process patterns in children with Spastic Cerebral Palsy (CP). Thirty children between the ages of 6 to 18 years were chosen (19 males and 11 females). The speech samples were collected using 160 single words and analyzed to see patterns of phonological processing. After three months of intervention, these children were reassessed. The findings revealed 54 types of phonological processes during pre-assessment in spastic cerebral palsied children, substitution of speech sounds were found to occur more frequently than other types of processes. In word level, the majority of the children had a higher frequency of occurrences in the final and medial positions than in the initial position. More types of phonological processes and a higher frequency of occurrences were observed. The study concluded that identifying phonological processes will support speech-language pathologists in planning interventions.

Keywords: Phonological Processes, Cerebral Palsy, Intervention

Introduction

Speech is a verbal way of message transmission that requires the perfect coordination of oral muscle movements to produce sounds and linguistic units. Language, on the other hand, includes intricate laws that control sounds, words, phrases, meaning, and use. These laws underpin a person's ability to interpret and formulate language. The rules of language are divided into five categories: pragmatics, semantics, syntax, morphology, and phonology [1]. One of the most important aspects of language is phonology. It includes speech sound generation as well as linguistic understanding of the sound system and sound patterns [2]. Phonological dysfunction is the result of a breakdown in the sound and the sound pattern in spoken language. It represents a person's impairment of phoneme representation and organization inside the language system. Phonological disorder is defined as the dysfunction in the arrangement of sound and its sequence in a specific language [3].

It has been established that even normal children during their development present with errors that reflect the simplifications during the gradual processes of acquiring an adult speech sound system. These simplifications are very common and are a predictable part of phonological development. These phonological processes are typically resolved as children mature and refine their speech sounds to align with those of adults. However, any disruption in phonological development can lead to a substantial number of speech sound errors when children communicate with others, resulting in communication breakdowns [4]. SLPs evaluate and treat children with communication impairments [5].

Cerebral Palsy (CP) is the most prevalent form of motor disability in children, affecting around two children out of every thousand live births [6], [7]. Cerebral palsy refers to a set of conditions marked by non-progressive abnormalities in movement and posture. These conditions are acquired in early childhood due to lesions on the developing brain [8], [9]. Spastic type is the most frequent movement disorder, & it is distinguished by abnormal voluntary control, heightened resistance to passive stretch, and hyper reflexes [10]. This prevalent neurological disorder, which emerges in the perinatal or early childhood period, significantly influences a person's overall development, particularly their communication abilities. Furthermore, these motor impairments often affect child's speech and language development, leading to phonological delay or disorder [11].

Literature Review

Studies have reported that children with disordered speech processes were similar to those seen in normal children. However, exact changes were established, mainly related to the use of processes by children with disordered speech. It was indicated that children with CP produced vowels more accurately than consonants [12]. Vowels produced with rounded lips and high tongue placement were less accurate than mid vowels and those produced with low and forward tongue placement. The production of bilabial

sounds was more accurate than any other consonant production with movements and found to be the most difficult, although it was claimed that voiced consonants and nasal sounds were more accurate than unvoiced consonants, while fricatives and glides were produced with less precision [13].

A child with left hemiplegia with speech errors i.e the dysarthric errors resulted from an articulatory or phonological deviance [14]. This author also analyzed using a natural phonological analysis to explore phonological processes. Results indicated that the phonological system of the subject was systematic and rule-governed and that the processes operating upon the phonological systems were attributable to deviant speech musculature. Similarly, speech intelligibility in fifty individuals with CP were also investigated [15]. The main findings were errors in speech sound production that primarily pertained to improper consonant placement and manner of production. These errors were found to be in word-initial and final consonants. Athetoid speakers performed poorer than spastic CP speakers on varied tasks. On analysis of their speech error patterns showed that these variations were dependent on severity of the problem.

On the other hand, perceptual phonetic analysis to profile the speech sound errors in twenty two Cantonese-speaking individuals with dysarthria due to CP [14]. They were examined for precision of error production and incorrect speech sound pattern produced using phonological process analysis. It was identified that no marginal changes noted in error accuracy based on CP type, gender, or age. Diphthong reduction, primarily attributed to neurological impairment, was more prevalent in speakers with athetosis. Frequencies of substitution errors were higher than distortion errors. These results have clinical significance for the evaluation of Cantonese speakers with CP.

In contrast, the speech profile of adult with CP using phonological processes analysis were profiled [16]. Speech samples were elicited using pictures of the Tamil Articulation Test [17] and picture story sequences of a familiar Panchatantra story. The results indicated that the frequency of fronting, stopping, gliding of liquids, devoicing, vocalization, final consonant deletion, initial consonant omission, backing, and consonant harmony in subjects with CP. Sound-by-sound analysis revealed more substitution errors, followed by omissions, distortions, and additions. A similar study examined the speech patterns of adults and children with spastic CP in Telugu language. A study shown that 60% of the errors were substitution errors, omission and distortion errors 3.5% [18]. Children and adults both had fronting, backing, and stopping errors. On comparing children and adult, children had more significant errors than adults (29.33% and 14%, respectively). These findings contribute to our basic understanding of the neuromotor basis of articulation and therapeutic options required for a person with CP. Phonological processes in Tamil-speaking children with spastic CP was investigated [19]. The study included fifteen CP children aged 8 to 13 years and fifteen typically developing Tamil speaking youngsters aged 3-6 years. The findings revealed that 16 phonological processes were reported in children with spastic CP. Final consonant omission, syllable simplifications, cluster reduction, and pausing were more common than

others. A total of 13 phonological processes were discovered in normal children such as final consonant deletion, syllable reduction, cluster simplification, pausing, backing, palatalization, lateralization, and nasal assimilation.

The effectiveness of treatment for functional phonological disorder in children were assessed [20]. Positive benefits of phonological therapy was assessed, with a focus on effects of treatment procedures enhancing speech intelligibility, as well as various treatment comparisons enabled improved sound production in children. Phonologically treated children exhibited both broad and limited changes in their sound systems, which enhanced their communicative abilities and overall speech clarity. Three modalities of therapy for children with developmental phonological problems were explored [21]. These children were treated with the following methods: phonological contrast, core vocabulary, and PROMPT (Prompts for Restructuring Oral Muscular Phonetic Targets). Throughout the program, children exhibited correct articulatory production and clarity of the conversational speech greatly improved. Children who repeatedly made non-developmental errors benefited most from the treatment program that is based on training children through rule governed phonemic system and also by use of phonemic contrast. Children who made inconsistent errors benefited the most from the core vocabulary strategy, which significantly improved consistency of performance.

The effect of varied contrasts in phonological therapy was also investigated [22]. Nineteen children received six hours of training and counseling. They were divided into two groups at random. In one cluster of participants (n=9) minimal pair intervention program was provided. The other group of children (n=10) received treatment that targeted sound contrasts that differed across specific traits. Children improved significantly in speech correctness, and the frequency of error patterns was reduced after the therapy.

Speech-language pathologists have primarily focused on phonology within the realm of speech sound disorders. It is imperative to establish an accurate diagnosis before initiating treatment for phonological disorders in children. Careful consideration must be given to the phonological patterns exhibited by these children. A fundamental guiding principle is to select sounds that children can readily imitate, as this can significantly enhance their speech intelligibility. Therefore, gaining comprehensive insights into the phonological challenges faced by children with CP is of paramount importance. This research holds the potential to assist speech-language pathologists in devising effective remediation programs for children dealing with phonological disorders.

Children affected by CP often confront limitations in their ability to acquire speech sounds. Even among those with cerebral palsy devoid of related impairments, the development of speech sounds acquisition proves to be a formidable challenge. Furthermore, the individual's capacity to produce speech sounds is intricately linked to neuromuscular activity. A deeper understanding of these challenges is crucial for

identifying relevant intervention strategies aimed at enhancing their communication skills and fostering their societal engagement. Consequently, delving into the exploration of phonological abnormalities and the patterns of phonological processes in children with CP is an area of great interest.

In the context of India, research related to the identification and management of phonological processes in children with CP remains limited. Notably, the sounds available for usage, the permissible sequencing of these sounds, and the rules or processes governing these sounds can vary among languages [23]. Consequently, investigating phonological processes, their identification, and effective management in Tamil-speaking children with spastic CP presents an intriguing avenue for research.

Methods

Subjects

The current study employed a purposive sampling strategy, comprising thirty Tamil-speaking youngsters with CP, ranging in age from 6 to 18 years (Mean Age=13.09 years). Formal language assessment was carried out using E-REELS [23] to assess all the youngsters. Subjects included those with a language age of 2.8 to 6.5 years, spastic CP with mild to moderate intellectual impairment (as per the psychologist's report), and epilepsy (noted in only three children who had recovered after medication, as reported by a parent) in the current study. Conversely, subjects were excluded if they had hearing loss, visual impairment, or autism spectrum disorders.

Stimulus Word List

In order to evaluate phonological processes in children, a comprehensive set of 160 di- and three syllabic words, encompassing consonants (n=18), ten vowels (n=10), and diphthongs(n=2), were meticulously chosen to represent a broad spectrum of speech sounds in various positions, including the initial, medial, and final positions. These word selections were curated from a foundational Tamil picture book, ensuring their relevance and appropriateness for the assessment. To establish the content validity of this word set, five experienced speech-language pathologists and three experienced linguists was actively engaged in the assessment process.

Procedure

Prior to data collection, informed oral consent was obtained from the parents or caregivers of all children participating in the study. The assessment sessions were conducted individually by the investigator in a quiet and distraction-free environment, ensuring that the youngsters were comfortable. During the assessment, the children were instructed to repeat words one at a time, with a 5-second interval following the investigator's presentation, and their speech productions were meticulously recorded using a Transcend

MP 330 audio recording device. Subsequently, following three months of dedicated phonological training, these children underwent a comprehensive review to evaluate the impact of the intervention.

Intervention

Description of remediation in the present study; Subject X was six years old. The subject had been identified as Spastic CP by 2 years of age. The child had been undergoing speech-language therapy and had been assessed using words and stories to identify phonological processes. Additionally, speech samples were recorded and analyzed following the collection of her speech data. The identified phonological processes were the focal point for phonological remediation. The intervention methods chosen for this subject included cycles therapy and maximal contrast therapy, followed by minimal pair therapy.

Intervention data sheet: A 6-year-old girl with a language age of 4 years presented herself to the department, reporting difficulty in speaking clearly and age-appropriately. Following the evaluation, the child was diagnosed with a speech sound disorder, with identified phonological processes including palatal fronting, velar fronting, bilabial backing, dental backing, liquid stopping, final consonant deletion, and nasal assimilation. The targeted sounds for intervention were /c/, /ŋ/, /ŋ/, /t/, /k/, /r/, /p/, /t/, and /m/. The therapy sessions were conducted for 45 minutes weekly, three times a week. The selected intervention approaches encompassed phonological contrast therapies and cycle therapy. The remediation process involved several stages: therapy initially focused on easier phonemes before progressing to more challenging ones, followed by syllables and words containing the targeted sounds. Subsequently, words with the most significant contrast to the target sounds were introduced, then those with minimal differences. The intervention also extended to words with the target sounds used in sentences and paragraphs. Remediation continued until the target sounds were successfully acquired by the subject. These steps were conveyed to both the parents and a special teacher involved in the subject's education. The subject's speech samples were recorded on a monthly basis, and feedback was provided to both the mother and the subject

Transcription

By listening to the recorded speech samples as many times as needed, they were transcribed. Furthermore, 30% of the speech samples were re-checked/listened to for incorrect words by three undergraduate speech-language pathology interns and one speech-language pathologist. For phonetic transcription of the recorded voice materials, the International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA) [24] was employed.

Statistical Analysis

For the investigation of phonological processes, In 1990, it was proposed an approach to enhance phonological process extraction from picture-word articulation tests. In Tamil, consonants and vowels occur in initial, medial, and final positions. The analysis involved separate tables for consonants and vowels, recording their frequency in each position. The data was organized to outline phonological processes and overall occurrences. This aimed to offer a comprehensive understanding of phoneme patterns in different positions during the test. In the current study, in addition to the investigator, two Ph.D. in Linguistics scholars with experience in phonological process analysis re-analyzed 10% of the transcribed speech samples. In the event of a disagreement among the three judges, the identified pattern was double-checked with a linguistics assistant professor. Following approval from the assistant professor, the final phonological patterns were incorporated into the current study.

Tabulated data's were analyzed in two ways. 1. Qualitative analysis and 2. Quantitative analysis. The qualitative analysis was done using phonological process analysis. The classification of phonological processes according to the analysis of present study (Figure 1). The quantitative analysis was applied to describe the analysis of phonological processes identified in children with spastic CP. The Mean, Standard deviation, two-way ANOVA, P-value, and t-test were used for phonological processes in each category observed among children with CP.

Figure 1

Classification of Phonological Processes

Results

The results of the present study were discussed within two primary categories of phonological processes (consonants and vowels), which were further subdivided into four subcategories: syllable structure, substitution, assimilation, and vowel processes. These processes were identified in children with spastic CP at the word level. The results of the children with CP were discussed with the mean, standard deviation, two-way ANOVA, t-test, p-value, and the frequency of occurrence. The number of children who demonstrated each process was discussed all positions (initial, medial and final) at the word level.

Qualitative Analysis

Quantitative analysis was done under two main categories of phonological processes (consonants and vowels) which are further divided into four subcategories of phonological processes namely; syllable structure, substitution, assimilation, and vowel processes identified in children with spastic CP in word level.

Syllable Structure Processes

It was identified that the number of children with CP who demonstrated syllable structure processes before and after therapy (Table 1). The number highlighted in brackets reflects the range of frequency of phonological process occurred among children with CP. Children with cerebral palsy showed 7 syllable structural processes.

Table 1

Number of children demonstrating syllable structure processes among pre and post-therapy children with CP

Syllable Structure Processes	Pre- therapy N=30			Post therapy N=30		
	Positions					
	Initial	Medial	Final	Initial	Medial	Final
Consonant deletion	10(1-14)	22(1-11)	26(1-18)	6(1-5)	16(1-2)	17(1-6)
Syllable deletion	10(1-3)	17(1-11)	16(1-16)	1(3)	14(1-4)	4(1-6)
Metathesis	---	3(1-2)	---	---	2(1)	---

Note: The number in parenthesis represents the range of the number of times a process occurred among the children with cerebral palsy

Consonant Deletion

It was also illustrated (Table 1) that in the pre-therapy group of children, 10 individuals exhibited initial consonant deletion within a frequency range of 1-14. In the medial position, 22 children demonstrated medial consonant deletion within a frequency range of 1-11, and in the final position, 26 children exhibited this phenomenon within a frequency range of 1-18. Conversely, following the intervention, 6 children displayed initial consonant deletion within a frequency range of 1-5. In the medial position, 16 children demonstrated medial consonant deletion within a frequency range of 1-2, and in the final position, 17 children exhibited this occurrence within a frequency range of 1-6.

Syllable Deletion

Before the intervention, 10 children demonstrated initial syllable deletion, with frequencies ranging from 1-3. In the medial position, 17 children exhibited medial syllable deletion within a frequency range of 1-11, and in the final position, 16 children displayed this phenomenon within a frequency range of 1-16. After the intervention, only one child exhibited initial syllable deletion, and in the medial position, 14 children displayed medial syllable deletion with frequencies ranging from 1-4. In the final position, 4 children demonstrated this phenomenon with frequencies ranging from 1-6.

Metathesis

Metathesis was observed in 3 children from the pre-therapy group, with a frequency range of 1-2 in the medial position. In the post-therapy group, 2 children exhibited metathesis, but only in the medial position.

Table 2

Syllable structure processes among pre and post-therapy children with CP

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F-Value critical
Positions	114.0833	1	114.083	8.217	0.035	6.607
Processes	401.4167	5	80.283	5.782	0.038	5.050

Note: $P \leq 0.05$ indicates statistically significant

The difference among pre and post-therapy group comparison (Table 2) of syllable structure processes in children with CP is statistically accepted since the obtained p-value is significant ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, it is concluded that both in positions and subtypes of phonological processes, there is a significant improvement in the syllable structure processes among children with CP after the intervention. (Figure 2) shows that syllable structure processes of both consonant and syllable deletion in pre-therapy were high in the number of occurrences when compared to post-therapy children with cerebral palsy.

Figure 2

Syllable structure processes among pre and post-therapy children with CP

Substitution Processes

Data on the occurrences of substitution processes (Table 3) in children with CP were noted pre and post therapy. The numbers within parentheses indicate the variability in the frequency of these processes among the children who exhibited them. It was observed that a total of 19 substitution mechanisms were identified in children with CP.

Table 3

Number of children demonstrating substitution processes among pre and post therapy children with CP

Substitution Processes		Pre-therapy N=30			Post therapy N=30		
		Positions					
		Initial	Medial	Final	Initial	Medial	Final
Fronting	Dental	3(1-2)	1(1)	---	1(1)	2(1)	---
	Alveolar	---	12(1-2)	4(1)	---	7(1-3)	2(1)
	Palatal	13(1-12)	12(1-8)	13(1-9)	3(1-9)	6(1-4)	6(1-7)
	Retroflex	---	15(1-8)	16(1-7)	---	6(1-4)	4(1-4)
	Velar	5(1-7)	11(1-5)	8(1-3)	---	5(1-2)	2(2-5)
Backing	Bilabial	7(1-13)	4(1-7)	4(1-8)	5(1-4)	2(1-2)	2(1-3)
	Dental	9(1-5)	11(1-13)	8(1-9)	5(1-3)	4(1-5)	2(2-4)
	Alveolar	---	3(1)	2(1-2)	---	1(1)	1(2)
	Palatal	1(1)	4(1-2)	5(1)	---	---	2(1)
	Retroflex	---	5(1-4)	4(1-14)	---	2(1-2)	---
Gliding	Liquid	1(1)	13(1-10)	12(1-12)	---	6(1-3)	9(1-2)
	Stop	---	9(1-4)	10(1-10)	---	1(1)	5(1-3)
Stopping	Liquid	---	18(1-7)	15(1-7)	1(1)	10(1-3)	10(1)
	Glide	1(1)	6(1-2)	3(1-3)	---	1(1)	---
	Fricative	---	---	1(1)	---	---	---
Glide Liquiding		---	3(1)	2(1)	---	1(1)	---
Stop Liquiding		---	2(1)	1(1)	---	3(1)	2(1-2)
Fricativization		1(10)	---	1(2)	---	---	---
Liquid Replacement		---	11(1-7)	8(1-5)	---	1(2)	1(4)

Note: The number in parenthesis represents the range of the number of times a process occurred among the children with cerebral palsy

Fronting

Out of 30 children in the pre-therapy group, 21 children demonstrated fronting (dental, palatal, and velar) in the initial position, with frequencies ranging from 1 to 12. In the medial position, 41 children exhibited fronting (dental, alveolar, palatal, retroflex, and velar) with frequencies ranging from 1 to 8. In the final position, 41 children displayed fronting (alveolar, palatal, retroflex, and velar) with frequencies ranging from 1 to 9. In contrast, within the post-therapy group of 30 children, 4 children displayed fronting (dental and palatal) in the initial positions, with frequencies ranging from 1 to 9. In the medial position, 26 children demonstrated fronting (dental, alveolar, palatal, retroflex, and velar) with frequencies ranging from 1 to 4. In the final position, 14 children exhibited fronting (alveolar, palatal, retroflex, and velar) with frequencies ranging from 1 to 7 (Figure 3).

Figure 3*Fronting processes among pre and post-therapy children with CP***Backing**

Among 30 children belonging to pre-therapy group, 17 children demonstrated backing (bilabial, dental & palatal) in the frequency range of 1-13 in the first and in the medial location, 27 children demonstrated backing (bilabial, dental, alveolar, palatal & retroflex) in the frequency range of 1-13 and, in final 23 children exhibited backing (bilabial, dental, alveolar, palatal & retroflex) in the frequency range of 1-14. On the other hand, among 30 post-therapy group, 17 children exhibited backing (bilabial, dental & palatal) in the frequency range of 1-13 initial positions, and in medial 27 children observed backing (bilabial, dental, alveolar, palatal & retroflex) in the frequency range of 1-13 and, in final 23 children seen backing (bilabial, dental, alveolar, palatal, & retroflex) in the frequency range of 1-14 (Figure 4).

Figure 4*Backing processes among pre and post therapy children with CP***Gliding**

Gliding was found in both the medial and terminal regions of liquid and stop sounds. One child in the pre-therapy group demonstrated liquid gliding once in an initial position, 22 children in the medium group exhibited gliding (liquid & Stopping) in the frequency range of 1-10, and 22 children in the final group exhibited gliding (liquid & stop) in the frequency range of 1-12. Among the 30 post-therapy children, 7 showed gliding in the frequency range of 1-3 medial positions, and 14 showed gliding (liquid & stop) in the frequency range of 1-3.

Stopping

Stopping was observed in liquid, glide, and fricative sounds. However, fricative stopping was occurred in one child once among pre-therapy group and not observed in the post therapy group. Stopping (glide) was observed in one child once in an initial position and medial 24 children exhibited (glide & liquid) in the frequency range of 1-7 and, in the final 18 children exhibited (liquid & glide) in the frequency range of 1-7. Among the post therapy group, 1 child exhibited liquid stopping once in an initial position, and in the medial 11 children exhibited stopping (liquid & glide) in the frequency range of 1-3, and, in the final liquid stopping exhibited in 10 children in once. Minimally occurred substitution processes were glide liquidizing, stop liquidizing, fricativization, and liquid replacement among pre-therapy. However, the liquid replacement was seen in 18 children in the pre-therapy group in the frequency range of 1-7 in the medial and final position, and in the post-therapy group 1 child in the medial and final position in 4 times.

Table 4

Substitution processes among pre and post-therapy children with CP

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F-Value critical
Positions	968.625	19	50.980	6.417	0.026	1.697
Processes	488.875	5	97.775	12.308	0.003	2.310

Note: $P \leq 0.05$; $P \leq 0.01$ indicates statistically significant

The difference (Table 4) among pre and post-therapy group comparison of substitution processes in children with CP is statistically accepted since the obtained p-value is significant ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, it is concluded that both in positions and subtypes of phonological processes, there is a significant improvement in substitution processes among children with CP after the intervention (Figure 5).

Figure 5

Other substitution processes among pre and post-therapy children with CP

Assimilation Processes

The number of children with CP (Table 5) demonstrated assimilation processes before and after therapy. The number in brackets reflects the range of frequency of procedure occurred among the children who demonstrated it. There were a total of 12 assimilation processes reported among individuals with CP.

Table 5

Number of children demonstrating assimilation processes among pre and post-therapy children with CP

Assimilation		Pre-therapy N=30			Post therapy N=30			
		Positions						
		Initial	Medial	Final	Initial	Medial	Final	
Assimilation	Bilabial	---	2(1)	1(3)	---	---	---	
	Dental	1(1)	2(1)	---	---	---	---	
	Palatal	---	4(1-4)	3(2-4)	---	---	---	
	Retroflex	1(1)	1(2)	2(1)	---	---	---	
	Velar	---	2(1-3)	---	---	---	---	
	Glide	---	---	1(1)	---	---	---	
	Vowel	---	1(1)	---	---	---	---	
	Nasal	1(1)	5(1-7)	4(1-5)	---	---	---	
Nasalization			3(1-3)	13(1-11)	8(1-3)	---	7(1-3)	2(1)
Denasalization			3(1-3)	11(1-9)	8(1-6)	---	4(1-5)	5(1-3)
Reduplication			---	3(1-5)	---	---	---	---
Voicing			3(1-2)	---	---	---	---	---

Note: The number in parenthesis represents the range of the number of times a process occurred among the children with cerebral palsy

In the pre-therapy group, consisting of 30 children, assimilation processes were observed across bilabial, dental, palatal, retroflex, velar, glide, vowel, and nasal sounds, within a frequency range of 1-7, encompassing initial, medial, and final positions. In contrast, among the 30 children in the post-therapy group, no assimilation processes were observed, with the exception of nasalization and denasalization. Nasalization and denasalization were identified in the pre-therapy group within the frequency range of 1-11, occurring at all word positions. After the therapy, these processes were observed within a reduced frequency range of 1-5, primarily in the middle and end positions.

Table 6

Assimilation processes among pre and post-therapy children with CP

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F-Value critical
Positions	234.4861	11	21.316	7.600	0.009	1.967
Processes	106.5694	5	21.313	7.599	0.001	2.382

Note: $P \leq 0.001$ indicates statistically significant

The difference among pre and post-therapy group (Table 6) comparison of assimilation processes in children with CP is statistically accepted since the obtained p-value is significant ($p < 0.01$). Therefore, it is concluded that both in positions and subtypes of phonological processes, there is a significant improvement in assimilation processes among children with CP after the intervention. Assimilation processes (Figure 6) were observed in the high frequency of occurrence among pre-therapy children when compared to post-therapy children.

Figure 6

Assimilation processes among pre and post-therapy children with CP

Vowel Processes

Number of children with CP (Table 7) demonstrated vowel processes before and after therapy were identified. The number in parenthesis reflects the range of how many times a procedure occurred among the children who demonstrated it. There were 13 vowel processes found in children with CP.

Table 7

Number of children demonstrating vowel processes in the pre and post-therapy children with CP

Vowel		Pre-therapy N=30			Post therapy N=30		
		Positions					
		Initial	Medial	Final	Initial	Medial	Final
Vowel	Fronting	3(1-2)	5(1-4)	3(1-3)	---	1(1)	1(1)
	Backing	6(1-3)	10(1-6)	4(1-6)	1(1)	2(2)	2(1-2)
	Lengthening	3(1-2)	6(1-3)	2(1-3)	---	1(1)	---
	Shortening	12(1-5)	3(1-2)	2(1)	2(1)	1(1)	---
	Raising	4(1-11)	3(1-2)	---	---	2(1-2)	---

	Lowering	8(1-4)	9(1-2)	7(1-8)	4(1-2)	1(1)	1(4)
Vowel deletion		9(1-5)	1(1)	1(1)	1(1)	---	---
Monophthongation		5(1-2)	---	10(1-6)	1(1)	---	5(1-2)
Diphthongation		1(1)	---	8(1-6)	---	---	---
Diphthong deletion		1(1)	---	1(1)	---	---	---

Note: The number in parenthesis represents the range of the number of times a process occurred among the children with cerebral palsy

Fronting, backing, lengthening and shortening of vowels, vowel raising, vowel deletion, monophthongation, diphthongation, and diphthong deletion were observed among pre and post-therapy children with CP (Figure 8). However, more number of children demonstrated among pre-therapy group when compared to post-therapy group, and the frequency of occurrence ranged from 1-11 in initial, 1-6 in medial and, in final 1-8 among pre-therapy group. Among post therapy children demonstrated in the frequency range of 1-4. It is evident from above that the vowel processes observed more number of children in the high frequency of occurrence among pre-therapy when compared to post-therapy group.

Table 8

Vowel processes among pre and post-therapy children with CP

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F-Value critical
Positions	108.0167	9	12.001	1.937	0.070	2.095
Processes	184.15	5	36.83	5.947	0.000	2.422

Note: $P \leq 0.001$ indicates statistically significant

Figure 8

Other vowel processes among pre and post-therapy children with CP

The difference among pre and post-therapy group (Table 8) comparison of vowel processes in positions in children with CP is statistically not accepted since the obtained p-value is significant ($p= 0.07$) and there was an significant improvement in vowel processes in children with CP after the intervention. Vowel processes (Figure 7) occurred in more frequency range in pre-therapy when compared to post-therapy group.

Table 9

Comparison of Pre and Post therapy phonological processes

Word	Group	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value
Syllable structure	Pre	17.88	19.09	4.03	0.001 S
	Post	3.57	3.68		
Substitution	Pre	27.91	22.88	4.60	0.001 S
	Post	7.24	8.10		
Assimilation	Pre	4.91	5.49	3.69	0.001 S
	Post	1.00	1.91		
Vowel	Pre	11.50	9.96	5.53	0.001 S
	Post	1.17	2.41		

Note: S-Significant at 0.001 level $P \leq 0.001$

Figure 7

Vowel processes among pre and post-therapy children with CP

It was shown that mean, standard deviation, t-test, and p-value of pre and post-therapy among four subcategories of phonological processes (Table 9) at the word level. Regarding the syllable structure processes, there was a significant difference among the children between pre and post-test p-value < 0.01 since obtained t' value is significant therefore after the intervention of phonological processes, children exhibited less frequency of occurrence in syllable structure processes. Further, regarding substitution,

assimilation, and vowel processes there is a significant difference between pre and post-therapy children with CP ($p < 0.01$) since it is concluded that the children exhibited very less frequency of occurrence among processes and overall speech intelligibility and general communicative functioning improved after the intervention in post-therapy children. Therefore the alternative hypothesis that there is a significant difference in phonological processes at the word level among the children is accepted. It was found that the mean scores (Figure 9) were high among pre-therapy children when compared to post-therapy children with CP after the phonological intervention.

Figure 9

Mean value of phonological processes among Pre and Post therapy children with CP

It was displayed that the within-group mean, standard deviation, F-value, and p-value for the four subcategories of phonological processes (Table 10) at the word level. Difference in scores was observed among the children within the experimental participants, with a p-value < 0.01 . This was supported by the significant t-value obtained, indicating that after the intervention of phonological processes, the children's performance improved in syllable structure, substitution, assimilation, and vowel processes. Consequently, the alternative hypothesis proposing a significant difference in phonological processes at the word level among the children was accepted.

Table 10*Comparison of phonological processes among chronological age within the post therapy group*

Processes	Chronological Age	Mean	SD	F-value	P-value
Syllable structure	3-7 years	5.50	4.95	15.35	0.001 S
	7-10 years	9.00	4.20		
	10-14 years	2.56	1.42		
	14-18 years	1.46	1.05		
Substitution	3-7 years	28.0	18.3	15.58	0.001 S
	7-10 years	10.0	4.60		
	10-14 years	7.00	4.18		
	14-18 years	2.46	2.67		
Assimilation	3-7 years	0.023	0.003	2.67	0.01 S
	7-10 years	2.67	3.67		
	10-14 years	1.11	1.05		
	14-18 years	0.31	0.63		
Vowel	3-7 years	0.051	0.02	3.03	0.01 S
	7-10 years	3.50	4.59		
	10-14 years	1.00	1.12		
	14-18 years	0.38	0.87		

Note: S-Significant at 0.001 level

Discussion

The findings reveal significant improvements in various phonological processes among children with spastic CP after intervention. It was also noted that substitution processes observed the number of children in the high frequency of occurrence among pre-therapy when compared to post-therapy group. The above findings supported by past finding [22], that the children improved significantly in speech correctness, and the frequency of error patterns was reduced during therapy. The study findings also [26] demonstrated the importance of both indepth understanding and descriptive profile of unintelligible speech. Both types of results were important highlighting in determining changes in a child's phonology over time.

The post-therapy analysis demonstrated a substantial decrease in the frequency of syllable structure processes, particularly in consonant and syllable deletion. The statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) indicates a noteworthy improvement in both positions and subtypes of syllable structure processes. The study identified a total of 19 substitution processes, with considerable reductions in fronting, backing, gliding, and stopping mechanisms post-therapy. Significant progress was observed in assimilation processes, with

a marked reduction in frequency post-therapy. Nasalization and denasalization, initially prevalent, notably decreased in the medial and final positions.

While improvements were noted in vowel processes after therapy, statistical significance ($p=0.07$) was not achieved. Other vowel processes like vowel deletion, monophthongation, diphthongation, and diphthong deletion demonstrated the maximum number of children in pre-therapy when compared to post-therapy. The current study's findings back up a prior study done [22], which found that various contrast phonological therapy reduced speech correctness and the number of error patterns. Similarly, it was also reported that the process approach targets specific groups of error pattern rather than single sounds and the use of meaningful contrasts [27], [28], [29] which incorporates techniques that facilitated generalization.

Post-therapy, children with cerebral palsy exhibited significantly reduced phonological process occurrences, leading to improved speech intelligibility and overall communicative function. This supports the hypothesis, consistent with [20] earlier findings on the positive impact of phonological intervention.

Conclusion

The study compared two groups of children with CP, one before therapy and the other after therapy. In comparison to the group that received therapy, the pre-therapy group had a larger number of children and a higher frequency of incidence of phonological processes. The research provided preliminary evidence supporting phonological development and phonological processes in Tamil-speaking children with CP. The study identified 54 phonological processes in children with spastic CP in the pre-therapy group and 18 processes in the post-therapy group. These processes included fricative stopping, fricativization, diphthong deletion (initial and final), vowel deletion (medial and final), prevocalic voicing, reduplication, and assimilation (bilabial, nasal, dental, palatal, retroflex, velar, glide, vowel). However, the other processes were present in the post-therapy group but with a lower number of children and a lower frequency of occurrence. Multiple processes were found in both children with normal development and those with spastic CP. Notably, spastic CP children exhibited a higher prevalence of multiple processes compared to typically developing children. Among children with spastic CP, the highest frequency of occurrence was observed in the final position, followed by medial and initial positions. In four subcategories of phonological processes, the maximum frequency of occurrence was found in syllable structure, which may be attributed to their limited oro-motor functioning, poor respiratory control, and the severity of spasticity among children with cerebral palsy.

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